

The War before the First War of Indian Independence: A Descriptive Account of the *Amara Sullya* Rebellion of 1837

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**Subrahmanya
Sharma. V**

Assistant Professor
Department Of English
University College Of Arts,
Tumkur University,
Tumakuru,Karnataka, India

Abstract *Amara Sullyada Dange* or The Rebellion of Amara Sullya, also referred to as the rebellion of Kalyanaswamy or *Kalyanappana Katakai*- the bold, futile attempt made by the peasants of Kodagu and South Canara in 1837 to restore the rule of Kodagu. It has been estimated that about 8000-10,000 people had participated in this rebellion against the British. Many historians, lacking proper historical perspective, have called this incident as “a mere attempt of robbery by unlawful elements”. The British too, in order to save themselves from embarrassment, had built narratives in the same line. Only a few, who are aware of the synthesis, magnitude and dimensions of the rebellion, have termed it as a war for freedom. The rebellion, though a failure, was able to convey a clear message to the imperial masters. An attempt has been made here to give a descriptive account of this *Amara Sullya* Rebellion, by weaving together various thin strands of information.

Keywords The First War, Indian Independence, Amara Sullya Rebellion of 1837.

Introduction *“For Distinguished Conduct and Loyalty to the British Government, Coorg 1837.”*
“Given in memory of the help and support to the British Government, in the month of April, 1837”

The above words are inscribed on the medals, guns and mementoes given to those who stood by the side of the East India Company/ British and lent their support in suppressing the less spoken and more forgotten war of independence waged by the combined front of the peasants of Kodagu and Dakshina Kannada in 1837, twenty years earlier than the widely acknowledged First War of Indian Independence.

Amara Sullyada Dange or The Rebellion of Amara Sullya, also referred to as the rebellion of Kalyanaswamy or *Kalyanappana Katakai*- are the names referred to the bold, futile attempt made by the peasants of Kodagu and South Canara in 1837 to restore the rule of Kodagu rulers. The British, in order to save themselves from humiliation and embarrassment, had blatantly recorded this valiant heroic struggle as a mere event of dacoity/robbery. Now, as India is making year round celebrations on the eve of its seventy fifth year of Independence, it is a worthy and equally important opportunity for us to know this war of independence that took place twenty years before the First War of Indian Independence.

Aim of study

In this paper an attempt has been made here to give a descriptive account of this *Amara Sullya* Rebellion, by weaving together various thin strands of information.

Review of Literature

For this research paper, various books, journals and websites on the relevant topic have been reviewed.

Main Text

The Background: Kodagu, Sullya and South Canara

Upto 1834, Sullya, a taluk in the present district of Dakshina Kannada in Karnataka, was under the Haleri Lingayath Rulers of Kodagu. Haleri rulers had established their rule over Kodagu as early as 1600 and ruled over Kodagu and Sullya with Madikeri as the capital. Chikkaveerarajendra, the last ruler in the lineage was not a people friendly ruler. His behavior invoked the wrath of the people quite easily. When the situation seemed to go out of control, the army of the East India Company under the Captaincy of Col. Fraser of Mysore captured the fort of Madikeri and dethroned Chikkaveerarajendra, who surrendered on 10th of April, 1834, got deported to Varanasi and later to London along with his daughter.

After taking control over Kodagu, the British Administration inducted some major economic and territorial changes for its administrative convenience. Sullya or Amara Sullya was separated from Kodagu and made a part of South Canara District that was annexed with the province of Madras. There was also a change in the mode of taxation. Earlier, tax was being collected in the form of kinds and now the British ordered that the tax was to be paid in cash. Taxes were levied on commodities like tobacco and salt, much to the displeasure of people and the peasantry in the region.

The Road towards Rebellion: Sullya as the epicenter.

A *jangama* or a wandering Lingayatha Saint by name Aparamapara Swamy, started making his presence in the places surrounding Sakaleshapura or Manjarabad in the year 1834. The people started to believe him to be Veerappa, the eldest son of Lingarajendra, the erstwhile ruler of Kodagu. As Chikkaveerarajendra was dethroned by then, the people had to accept Aparamparaswamy to be their leader. An alliance of farmers from Somavarapete, Harangi, Haleri and Hosaketi was made and they marched down to Sullya for more mobilization and further actions. Appayya Gowda and Mallappa Gowda of Koojugodu in Sullya were to lend their support. However, before their march reached Gowdalli, Aparamapara was caught by the British. He was sent to Tiruchinapalli Prison where he was imprisoned till 1869.

This attempt was followed by another, made by Kalyanappa/Kalyanaswamy or Kalyanasasava. He was a follower of Swami Aparamapara. He got enough support from the people by projecting himself as the second son of Lingarajendra. Divana Cheppudira Ponnappa proved this claim to be wrong in the presence of Captain Lee Hardy. However, the people continued their support to Kalyanaswamy. Huli Konda Nanjayya, Guddemane Appayya Gowda, Rama Gowda of Kedamabadi in Sullya, Koojugodu Brothers, Ukanna Banta of Peraje and Subraya Heggade of Kumbale too lent their support to him.

As Kalyanaswamy came to know that the British were planning to capture him too, he planned to escape to Wayanadu through Kodlipete. However, Captain Lee Hardy managed to capture Kalyanaswamy and put him in Mysore Prison.

The Rebellion of Amara Sullya: April, 1837

The news of Kalyanaswamy's arrest was known only to Huli Konda Nanjayya. However, the news was kept as a secret in order to retain unity among the rebel farmers. Upon the suggestions from Kedambadi Rama Gowda, it was decided to impersonate Puttabasava, a follower of Aparamaparaswamy and Kalyanaswamy and project him as Kalyanaswamy. The leaders- Huli Konda Nanjayya, Guddemane Appayya Gowda, Rama Gowda of Kedamabadi in Sullya, Koojugodu Brothers, Ukanna Banta of Peraje, two tribal brothers- Chetti Kudiya and Karthu Kudiya, Karadimale Anni Gowda, Karanika Krishnayya, Karanika Subbayya and Kosappa Gowda of Kolchar- along with the peasant folk assembled in Sullya with the intention of capturing Mangaluru. Subraya Heggade of Kumbale was to join them in Mangaluru with his troop.

The banner of Rebellion was raised on 5th of April, 1837, with the slaying of Amaldar Atluru Ramappayya who was in charge of the treasury at Bellare. After capturing valuables in the treasury, Puttabasava/ Kalyanaswamy made the historical *Istihar* and declared the re-annexation of Sullya with Kodagu, cancelled all taxes and abolished taxation on tobacco and salt. Panja, Puttur, Kadaba and Vitla easily surrendered to the advancing rebels. Lakshmappa Bangarasa of Nandaavara in Paane Mangaluru welcomed them and supported them by providing funds and cannons. Without facing any resistance, the rebels marched towards Mangalore. The Resident DC had already fled along with his family members and a couple of soldiers. The rebel farmers captured treasury, weapons and the prison. They hoisted their flag in Bavutagudde, a hill in the town of Mangalore.

The British, who were fleeing from Mangalore to Kannur, kill Subraya Hagade and his team when they encountered him and his troop on the river Nethravathi.

The Short Lasted Victory: Suppression, Trials and Execution of Rebels

The rebels were able hold on for 13 days. British army units arrived from Bombay, Thalasserry and Kannur and recaptured Mangalore in the wee hours of midnight. Appayya Gowda, Rama Gowda, Kukkanooru Chennayya, Puttabasappa alias Kalyanaswamy, the Kudiya Brothers managed to escape. Later, Puttabasappa was captured in Kodlipete. After a trial in Madikeri Fort, Lee Hardy ordered to hang him to death on 15th April, 1837.

Lakshmappa Bangarasa and many others were caught later. They were hanged to death and their bodies were left for the public's view in a place called Bikarnakatte in the town of Mangalore. The Kudiya brothers and Peraje Krishnayya were deported to Singapore. Guddemane Appaya Gowda was hanged on 31st October, 1837, in the fort of Madikeri.

Interpretations and Reflections

This incident is often referred to as "*Kalyanappana Katakayi*" or "the robbery raids of Kalyanappa". Many historians too, lacking proper historical perspective, have called this incident as "a mere attempt of robbery by unlawful elements". The British too, in order to save themselves from embarrassment, had built narratives in the same line. Only a few, who are aware of the synthesis, magnitude and dimensions of the rebellion, have termed it as a war for freedom. It has been estimated that about 8000-10,000 people had participated in this rebellion against the British. (Achar.pp.69-70)

Marks Cubbon, who was the then British Commissioner for Mysore, in his report to his higher authorities in London, had stated that "the rebellion took place from 29th March 1837 onwards. The rebels had marched from the border between Kodagu and South Canara and went towards Mangalore, covering places like Sullya, Subrahmanya, Puttur, Belthangady, Bantwala, Mulki, Kasaragod, Kumbale, Manjeshwara and Thalapady, attacking government offices, treasuries and not causing any harm to people and their properties. There was a widespread support from the people" (Achar.p.66).

Therefore, it can be judged clearly that freeing themselves and their lands from the British Regime was the utmost objective of the Amara Sullya rebellion of 1837. The rebellion, though failed, was able to convey a clear message to the imperial masters.

Introspection: Causes for Failure

1. Most of the rebels were peasants and agricultural labourers who lacked military and weapons training.
2. The fight was not waged in systematic manner. Most of the rebels went back to their homes after the victory. None has envisaged the need for maintaining a standing army.
3. The rebels did not possess sophisticated weapons like guns and cannons. Their weapons limited to swords, sickles and sticks. They did not think of acquiring better weapons either.
4. Some unruly elements started plundering people in the name of Kalyanaswamy. This made the rebellion unpopular in some parts of South Canara and Kodagu,
5. The British, on the other hand, used all the resources available at their disposal to counter and suppress the rebellion. Better espionage and police system, well trained army and the timely arrival of reinforcements from Bombay and Thalassery helped the British to suppress the rebellion and recapture Kodagu and Mangalore.
6. Traders, wealthy class and landlord class did not support this rebellion.
7. The unpleasant memories of a plundering and looting raid conducted in South Canara in 1800 by Gopa Gowda, a Commander under the Coorg Ruler were still fresh in minds of people in this region. Hence, many declined to support the cause of a Kodava Ruler. (Achar.pp.67-68).

Some important Representations of the Amara Sullya Rebellion:

Historical works on the Amara Sullya Rebellion have been a few- S.N, Deviprasad (*Gowdara Elu Beelu- Charitrika Avalokana*.2003, *Amara Sullyada Svaathantrya Samara* 1999), Dr. Purushothama Bilimale (*Amarasullyada Raitha Horata* 1834-1837) , Dr. Prabhakara Shishila(*Amara Kranti Veeraru* 2005), K. R. Vidhyadhara (*Kedambadi Ramagowda*), Dr. Palthadi Ramakrishna Achar (*1837ra Tulunaada Rautha Bandaya*. 2014) are some of the notable researchers and scholars who have tried to shed light on this memorable war of independence.

Niranjana, one of the famous novelists in Kannada, had written two novels- *Kalyanaswamy* and *Swamy Aparampara*- based on the events and leaders of the Amarasullya Rebellion.

Conclusion

Historiography of India's Independence movement is an ever evolving domain as ignored; less spoken incidents are unearthed and brought into limelight. Moreover, there is also a need to re read and re interpret the already constructed narratives on the basis of fresh evidences or reliable strands of information. India's freedom was a result of the contributions and struggles waged by both the known and unknown heroes. To ignore or to sideline their struggles is to leave lacunas in the collective historiography. From this perspective, it has been hoped that this article will provide an understanding of the Amara Sullya Rebellion that was fought against the British in the present Kodagu-Dakshina Kannada districts in the state of Karnataka.

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